

PIANO LEARNING METHODS

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Abstract: This article contains comments on effective methods and technologies of piano teaching. It is known that the art of music educates a person's positive qualities and shapes his aesthetic qualities.

Key words: Music culture, art, piano, musical instrument.

The problem we are exploring is extremely relevant for music teachers. Piano pedagogy concerns the field of educating the student's individuality. The main goal of a teacher teaching a child at a music school is not just to teach him to play any musical instrument, in our particular case, the piano, but to create conditions for the development of the child as a musician.

This means that the musical language should gradually become native for the child. The teacher needs to "open" the soul of the child for the perception of music, teach him to read the musical text, as they read the text, verbal, that is, to teach them to read not letters and words, but to understand the meaning behind them. All this means revealing the secrets of the instrument on which he creates, and the secrets of the organism through which he creates.¹

Consider the basic methods of learning to play the piano. The methodological literature presents a classification into three groups: the method of imitation, the method of emotional-volitional and intellectual influence.

Let us characterize the method of imitation. Its essence lies in the student's perception "by ear" of the musical material performed by the teacher and, after him, copying the musical technique "from hand". It should be emphasized that this method is most often used in working with children who are just starting their studies at a music school. However, one must take into account the fact that not all children are equally susceptible to music. If a child has learned to understand the teacher, his requirements, mastered the elements of his piano playing technique, then it is possible to predict successful results in this difficult work for the child. We also note that this method has a significant drawback. If the teacher does not properly master the technique of the game, that is, the level of his professionalism is not sufficient, then imitation can also give a negative result.

¹ Kharatova, S. K., & Ismailov, T. X. O. G. L. (2022). Use of innovative technologies in the educational process. *Science and Education*, 3(3), 713-718.

The next method is the method of emotional-volitional influence. The teacher, explaining to the child the legend of the creation of the work, the life story of the composer and other information about the work, seeks to awaken emotionality and inspiration in the student (for example, gesturing in a certain way, singing, showing pictures, etc.). Thus, by influencing the personality of the child, the teacher evokes bright musical performances in him and increases his creative activity. And sometimes technical tasks that seemed unsolvable for a child are successfully completed by him. But in this case, it must be remembered that the use of this method is possible subject to several conditions: the presence of the student's initiative and the level of development of his performing apparatus. As for the shortcomings of this method, we note the following - educating a student under the influence of someone else's will can lead to the development of creative passivity and pliability of the psyche to someone else's influence, so you can miss the "performing initiative" in the student. The teacher is obliged not to "stamp" students in his own image, but to quietly correct their development in the right direction.

Another method that is actively used by teachers in music schools is the method of intellectual influence. It is addressed to the consciousness of the student and is based on faith in one's strengths, musical abilities and abilities. This method requires the student to be as active as possible in learning to play the piano. It promotes the development of independence. But it must be remembered that excessive rationalization can harm the student in the development of his performing qualities.

Each of the described methods is actively used in the practice of teaching children in music schools and circles. Their use depends on the student himself,

the level of development of his musical abilities, the tasks that the teacher sets for him for a specific period of study. Therefore, a method that is used with one student may not be suitable for another. The teacher must be sensitive, flexible, possessing pedagogical technique and able to find an individual approach to each student.

For the successful teaching of children to play the piano, each teacher can practice various groups of methods, actively use the experience of advanced teachers, engage in a creative search for the most effective pedagogical techniques as part of the methods.

When looking for ways to teach piano playing, the teacher is required to display such qualities that could contribute to the comprehensive development of the student. These include: understanding the properties of the performing process, the ability to analyze it, the ability to “listen” and “hear” someone else’s performance, analyze it, formulate recommendations for improving the quality of performance, and identify the causes of children’s “failures” in performance.

It is equally important for the teacher to show the ability to accept the student's point of view and, together with him, look for a solution to the next tasks; the ability to correlate their understanding of the work and the performing process with the characteristics and capabilities of each student. To do this, it is necessary to have the ability to “reincarnate” to the right extent, that is, to ensure that the performing intentions and playing sensations of the student are experienced by the teacher as their own. In his work, the teacher should build on the level of development of the student's musical and pianistic state, and in each period of training with him, in order to find the "leading link" for the current work and outline a plan for the next one. And yet the main, most important condition for successful work with children is the calling of the teacher to musical pedagogical activity. Without a vocation, it is impossible for a student to become what a teacher should be: a model, a favorite mentor for the younger ones and a friend for the older ones. In musical pedagogy, the learning process is mastered by both: the student and the teacher, and thus the most important pedagogical principle is implemented: “teaching - learn!”. Of course, the teacher should not lose the leading role. Behind him is knowledge, experience, which the student does not yet have. But the teacher is "ahead", he should not "train" the student on the proposed ready-made sample, he only directs the student to search for one of the possible solutions to the artistic problem that corresponds to the level of his musical development, his personality - tastes, temperament and technical resources.

It is very important not to forget about the interaction of teaching methods and the development of the individual characteristics of the student. After all, the goal of modern music education is not just the development of the child's personality, but mainly the identification of his creative abilities, the preservation of physical and mental health.

An important thing when working with a child, especially "in the first couple", is the education of an artist in him - an artist. First of all, such qualities as patience, perseverance and attention, as well as a sense of responsibility for their work. This is what distinguishes the process of learning in a music school from learning in a general educational organization.²

Thus, using a variety of methods for teaching the piano, the teacher should strive to ensure the healthy and steady growth of the student. Work for the future. Strive not for a false speed of development of the student, but to ensure that the conditions for a new step forward are provided. Each task for a student and each of his successes should answer the question: what can we build on this in the future?

Based on the foregoing, we came to the conclusion that the level and quality of knowledge, skills and abilities of the student depends on the methods of teaching. Methods as a pedagogical category are the basis for teaching and educating children to be independent in mastering musical material, developing their performing qualities and creative initiative. Based on our own pedagogical experience, it should be emphasized that the underestimation of the capabilities of our children can lead to the "template" of the methods and techniques of music education. Using a variety of methods in his practical activities, the teacher is able to ensure that children acquire knowledge and skills at a deeper, creative level, which determines the high quality of their musical activity, and, accordingly, carry out full-fledged musical development.

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